

MORE ON *CLADOMELEA LONGIPES* (ARANEAE: ARANEIDAE)

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Abstract: The bolas spider *Cladomelea longipes* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877) has a wide distribution in Africa, and is known from Cameroon, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Zimbabwe and South Africa. In this paper we report on new information on their mating, feeding and egg cocoon construction.

Key words: Spider, mating, egg cocoon, feeding, Africa

In a recent publication by Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord (2019), the bolas spider, *Cladomelea longipes* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877) was reported from South Africa for the first time. *Cladomelea longipes* differs from its congeners in the colour of the body and shape of the abdomen and copulatory organs.

The carapace is greyish-pink and covered in dense setae, giving it a woolly appearance. The carapace is broad, rounded posteriorly, and narrowed anteriorly. The ocular tubercle is high and bears a row of three strong erect spines medially. The abdomen is triangular, dorsally pink, and infused with a grey guanophore and silky hair, giving it a woolly appearance. Two large, yellow, round tubercles are present on the antero-lateral corners of the abdomen, and four smaller white round tubercles are arranged in rows in between (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord (2019)).

I recently received some excellent photographs of *C. longipes* from Tinus Odendaal of a female he observed over a period of several weeks in Cameroon (Fig. 1). He was able to capture some of their interesting behavior, including using their bolas to catch moths, on camera.

Figure 1. *Cladomelea longipes* female on a leaf.

However, it was only when studying the photographs that we observed the very tiny black male in the vicinity of the female (Fig. 2a, b). The male, which is about 10x smaller than the female, is still undescribed. Of the species of *Cladomelea*, only the male of *C. akermani* Hewitt, 1923 is known, which was described by Leroy *et al.* (1998). The two males seem to be similar in shape and size. In *C. longipes*, the male's abdomen is decorated with a pale spot near the posterior end.

Figure 2. (a) *Cladomelea longipes* female, and to the top left the very small male; (b) Close-up of the very small undescribed male.

The mating process of *Cladomelea* spp. has never been recorded. A very interesting observation was made when the small male was observed sitting on the epigyne of the female on some of the photographs. The white spot on the abdomen of the male was clearly visible, indicating that he sits with his venter pressed against her epigyne. What is more interesting is that he stayed there for a few days, even while she was feeding (Fig. 3a, b).

Figure 3. (a, b) *Cladomelea longipes* female, ventral view, showing the tiny male sitting on her epigyne while she is still feeding.

Figure 4. (a) *Cladomelea longipes* female hanging from trapezium web, with bolas with two sticky droplets; (b) *Cladomelea longipes* female, swinging her leg with the bolas; (c) *Cladomelea longipes* female with the moth she has captured (left), while another moth landing on them (right).

The general behaviour of making the bolas (Fig. 4a) and swinging it around (Fig. 4b) was very similar to that of *C. akermani*. During the observation period, only moths were caught. It is still unknown whether *Cladomelea* spp. also release false pheromones to attract male moths. On one image (Fig. 4c) the female was feeding on a moth while another moth landed on them, having possibly been attracted by pheromones of the captured moth or false pheromone of the spider.

EGG COCOONS: The egg cocoon constructed by *C. longipes* differs from that of other known *Cladomelea* species. The female eventually constructed four egg sacs that were observed suspended 0.5 to 1.9 metres above the ground (Figs 5a, b).

Figure 5. (a,b) *Cladomelea longipes* female constructing egg cocoons that hang from reinforced silk threads

The incubation period is about 40 days. The spiderlings (>100) emerged and stay together for up to 36 hours after hatching (Fig. 6a,b). During breezier days they left the hatching site quicker. Ballooning was observed when few lift off with the breeze, attached to a length of silk.

Figure 6. (a,b). *Cladomelea longipes* egg cocoons with spiderlings

REFERENCES

- DIPPENAAR- SCHOEMAN, A.S. & FOORD, S.H. 2019. New records of *Cladomelea* from South Africa, including the first records of *C. longipes* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877) (Araneae, Araneidae) outside its type locality. *Check List* 15(6): 1-5.
- LEROY, J.-M., JOCQUÉ, R. & LEROY, A. 1998. On the behaviour of the African bolas-spider *Cladomelea akermani* Hewitt (Araneae, Araneidae, Cyrtarachninae), with description of the male. *Annals of the Natal Museum* 39: 1-9.
- LEVI, H.W. 2003. The bolas spiders of the genus *Mastophora* (Araneae: Araneidae). *Bulletin of the Museum of Comparative Zoology at Harvard College* 157: 309.
- ROFF, J. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2004. Description of a new species of *Cladomelea* bolas-spider from South Africa, with notes on its behaviour (Araneae: Araneidae). *African Invertebrates* 45: 1-6.